

Quality Control of Service in Hotels

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Abstract: Quality control of hotel services is a key aspect of the successful operation of this business. This abstract is devoted to the study of methods of quality control of service in hotels and their impact on customer satisfaction.

Keywords: Quality control, hotel services, customer feedback, customer satisfaction, negative feedback.

In the current economic situation, the struggle for customers is becoming more and more intense, and high-quality service is becoming the most important, if not the only advantage that can distinguish a company from competitors. It is good service that will encourage the client to return and bring friends, as well as buy more services and related products. According to numerous studies, on average, 65-80% of the company's turnover is provided by regular customers.

It is very important to control the quality of service. For employees who directly provide services, indicators of the quality of work are most often the percentage of overwriting to a particular specialist, his average check, the level of evaluation of his work by clients. For the rest of the staff, the indicator of personal effectiveness will be the level of overall customer satisfaction — the impression received from the company as a whole.

You can monitor customer satisfaction in various ways: a survey (personal, telephone); sending messages (SMS, email) with a request to evaluate the level of service received in a reply message or via an online link; installing remotes with buttons "Evaluate the quality of service". Each of these methods has its pros and cons, but none of them will be an effective tool for quality control of the service if it is not supplemented with the correct methodology.

When monitoring the quality of service, five important rules must be taken into account:

1. Motivating customers to evaluate the service

Loyal customers are ready to spend their energy on feedback from you, in most cases. This means that the final picture of customer satisfaction is often distorted.

One of the most effective ways to encourage a client not only to evaluate the quality of service, but also to return to you again — at the beginning of the service, tell him that you always give a 10% discount on the next visit if the client evaluates the quality of service at the end of the visit.

2. Measuring the number of customers who refused to give an assessment

A customer who is dissatisfied with your service will most likely not press any buttons or send SMS. Most likely, he will "vote so-so." Therefore, it is very important to measure not

only the number of positive or negative reviews, but also the number of visits when people did not want to waste time and emotions on feedback. It is the number of visits without evaluation that indicates the level of customer disloyalty.

3. Immediate response to customer dissatisfaction

A negative feedback from a client does not mean that he is disloyal. By spending energy on demonstrating dissatisfaction, the client most often shows that he is not completely disappointed in you and believes that he will be heard, and the cause of dissatisfaction has been eliminated. Make every effort to fix the problem and, after fixing it, personally invite the client to come back and evaluate the changes.

4. Unambiguous formulation of questions, ask various questions

The questions you ask your clients should not be interpreted in two ways. For example, the question "Evaluate the quality of service" will be understood by one as a request to evaluate the work of a particular employee, and the other — the office as a whole. At the same time, there is no need to choose any one question and ask all clients exactly that. Periodically change the questions you ask customers in order to comprehensively examine their impressions of your service. For example, you can put 3 questions in the monthly rotation: "Please rate my work" (assessment of a specific specialist); "Did you like it here today?" (assessment of the entire office as a whole); "Would you recommend us to your friends?" (this question is the most indicative when assessing customer satisfaction, in particular in leading companies, the number of positive responses to it is several times higher than the results of their lagging competitors).

5. Using the customer satisfaction indicator to motivate staff

This is a very good practice. But there is an "underwater reef" here: employees will consider this indicator biased towards them if customer satisfaction was influenced by circumstances beyond their control. In this case, the motivation system will have the opposite effect. To avoid this, determine in advance a clear sequence of actions of employees in case of emergency situations (for example, something broke) and a general algorithm of work in case of non-standard situations. Such instructions will help your staff to leave the client satisfied even in case of unforeseen problems.

We live in a time when often the only difference between the offers of different companies that the customer is able to see is the difference in the quality of service. The difference in your favor will create the client's disposition to contact you specifically.

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